

SOCIOLINGUISTICS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotatsiya

Language teaching is connected with sociolinguistics in many ways. Different social factors affect language teaching and language learning. This paper investigates the relationship between sociolinguistics and language teaching. Some social factors such as situation, context, and social setting that has roles in language teaching. It describes the main factors which influence linguistic choices and explains how well contemporary teaching can take account of them. It also investigates obvious variations in the use of language used by people belonging to varieties facets.

Kalit soʻzlar: language teaching, social factors, and sociolinguistics, language variation, social contexts.

Introduction

Language is a centre to social interaction in every society, regardless of location and time period. Language and social interaction have a reciprocal relationship: language shapes social interactions and social interactions shape language.

Learning language is getting through the teaching learning process indoor, outdoor, formal or non formal education. Teaching, learning language, sociocultural contexts and variations of language should be considered because it is influenced by the success of the learning a language. The teacher may not neglect the influences of a variety of languages and sociocultural contexts of the participants, especially in mother tongue or foreign language. This is due to the roles to easier the learners to gain the purposes of teaching learning language.

The terms of sociocultural contexts and variations of language may be covered in sociolinguistics study. In order to understand the phenomenon, broad knowledge of the process of language acquisition, second or foreign language education, sociolinguistics, linguistics, psycholinguistics, and specific knowledge of foreign language teaching techniques and methods of measurement and evaluation have become especially important. Sociolinguistics has become a very important role recent, and we have become aware the role of language not just as a means of communication,

but also a creator of social identity (Dunkley, 2013). Sociolinguistics is an interesting and important area of language for teachers because it deals with how the language is used and thought of in the real world.

What is Sociolinguistics?

Definitions of Sociolinguistics

There are several researchers or linguists give the definition of sociolinguistics in different perspective.

Yasemin (2013) defined sociolinguistics as the science that investigates the aims and functions of language in society. It attempts to explain how language differs from one context to another across geographical borders and how people in one context communicate with people in other contexts (e.g., non native-nonnative speakers; nonnative-native speakers; and so on). He's prone to learn language based on the sociocultural contexts, how the learners can communicate in one context with the others. Sali (2012), sociolinguistics is the interaction between language, culture, and society. Depending on the focus, virtually any study of language implicates a social connection because without this human component language itself would not exist. The language is linked to the interaction between language and culture, language and social phenomenon. According to Spolsky (2010) sociolinguistic is the study of the link between language and society, of language variation, and attitudes about language. It is supported by Hudson (1996) defined as a study of the relationship between language and social factors such as class, age, gender and ethnicity. Whereas Bell (1976) said it is a branch of anthropological linguistics that examines how language and culture are related, and how language is used in different social contexts. The study of stylistic and social variation of language (Wardhaugh, 2010). The study of language in relation to its social-cultural context (Van Dijk, 2009). Sociolinguistics is the study of the effect of any and all aspects of society, including cultural norms, expectations, and context on the way language is used (Trudgill, 2000).

The Subject of Sociolinguistics

Fishman (1971) defined sociolinguistics as the study of varieties, function, and speaker of the language. According to him, they are changeable, interacting, and modification in language society. According to Grimshaw, (1971), there are four kinds relationship between language and society as follows (1) language determine society; (2) sociocultural determine language; (3) co-variance between social facts and language; (4) language and society is determined by other factors such as culture, abstract structure or biological nature.

Sociolinguistic Approaches

At least there are three approaches of sociolinguistics: (1) de Saussure approach. Fishman stated connotation and a variety of language is associated with speech and individual not by language and society. The successful of communication because of

uniformity and homogeneity society used the same symbols; (2) the approach was pioneered by William Labov that emphasized to language varieties. The misconception between speakers occur because they do not have an equal sociocultural background. (3) Stylistic variety approach. The speakers use the language varieties in communication adapted to the situation.

Why Sociolinguistics is Necessary in Language Teaching?

Sociolinguistics is that branch of linguistics dealing with the influence of the society on language and vice-versa. Under this branch we deal with the problems faced in learning a language or, to say how a language is acquired and also how a language is modified according to different social circumstances. Through this we also come into contact with the traditional value of a language, which otherwise would have remained unknown to us. So, Sociolinguistics is an integral part in the study of language in common, and in the study of the impact of society over language. So, it is really important in the sphere of the study of language. As I told above that the teacher most focus, on words, grammar, and text contents in teaching language recently without considering the communication in its entirety, whereas in learning the language to use it, appropriate place(s) and cultural(s) of the language should be taken into consideration in addition of language itself that make the pupils will never be fluent in another language. Each language is used by different contexts, by different people, and for different reasons when the language is learnt. It is important to consider those factors to effectively communicate to others, which presumably the ultimate goal.

Conclusion

Based on the above discussion, I sum up that sociolinguistic has an important role in language teaching because it is consist of the study of the link between language and society, of language variation, the attitudes about language. It is noteworthy in learning language because it can give the suitable perspective of language.

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